

Ensuring employment and labor of persons with disabilities

Tashkent specialized number №1

for persons with disabilities

director of a vocational school

Vahobov Muradali Jalilovich

Tashkent specialized vocational

school No.1 for persons with disabilities,

social adaptation science teacher

Chorshanbiyev Avaz Eshkuvatovich

The development of each country is largely determined by the level of use of professional, intellectual and creative abilities of people. Including all categories of unemployed citizens (youth, disabled, women, people of retirement age, etc.) is of primary importance. The labor market is understood as a system that includes a complex of social and labor relations related to the terms of hiring labor, its use and exchange for living, its self-realization features, and the supply and demand mechanism. The labor market for persons with disabilities is a separate socio-demographic segment of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is subject to its own laws that must be taken into account in the employment policy. Therefore, the state undertakes to support the integration of disabled citizens who lack competitiveness and find it difficult to find work. The position of disabled people in society is determined by a number of objective and subjective factors: the level of material security, self-fulfillment in the professional sphere, education, satisfaction of rights and social guarantees. Unemployment among citizens with disabilities is distinguished by the specific weight of its negative consequences when considering employment problems. Illness or injury can cause a person to lose health, resulting in significant negative consequences in his life. Not only the physiological functions of the body are disturbed, but also the social, including professional, activity of a person is reduced. Eliminating the consequences of disability, restoring some of the vital functions lost in connection with it, as well as socially important qualities, allows a disabled person to become a full-fledged and equal member of society, to participate directly in the life of society, and contributes to its development. Labor activity has a special place in this process, it has a positive effect on the life of a disabled person. Employment supports the individual's physical, personal and professional recovery. The material well-being of persons with disabilities also increases significantly. A person's mental state changes, he stops feeling useless. His influence in the family, society, and state will increase. Under the influence of work,

the body develops compensation mechanisms that help eliminate a number of deficiencies caused by disability.

The United Nations Charter on Persons with Disabilities, adopted in 1980, states that the quality of life of persons with disabilities should not differ from the standard of living of the rest of the population. Importantly, this goal is achieved not through social donations of the state, individual organizations and individuals, but through a system of social, organizational, economic, psychological and other measures that allow the disabled person to adapt to new conditions. The employment rights of persons with disabilities have long been the focus of the United Nations and other international organizations. The "Standard rules of equal opportunities for persons with disabilities" adopted in 1993 defined the most problematic directions for creating favorable conditions for the inclusion of this category of citizens in the life of their country. In one of the paragraphs, the issue of employment of disabled people is considered separately. It states: "States should recognize the principle of giving persons with disabilities access to their human rights, particularly in the field of employment. They should have equal opportunities to engage in effective and profitable employment in the labor market, both in the countryside and in the city." Building market relations is not only positive, but also negative, which is associated with increased requirements for employees. As a result, the number of citizens belonging to the category of non-competitive persons is constantly increasing. All these processes are especially intensified during socio-economic crises. In this regard, the problem of employment of disabled people acquires new features. On the one hand, employment issues are extremely important for them, on the other hand, not everyone has the opportunity to fulfill their needs in professional activities. People with disabilities entering the labor market differ in age, gender, education and professional level, health and attitude to life. Among those recognized as unemployed are those who have become disabled as a result of illness, injury, those who have been injured in production and during military operations, and those who have been disabled since childhood. All of them are divided into several groups for different reasons. The following features are important for solving the issue of employment:

1. With the level of work ability (able to work, disabled, temporarily disabled or able to work in limited places, under favorable working conditions)
2. The nature of the person's disease (mobile, partially mobile, immobile).

Depending on the membership of a certain group, the issues of employment and employment of disabled citizens are resolved. The relatively low rate of employment of people with disabilities is largely explained by the uncertain attitude to life and the lack of required professional education and work experience. The

specific situation of disabled people in the labor market is determined by a number of factors:

1. Maintaining stereotypes. Many employers consider the lack of work experience of people with disabilities, the inability to effectively perform their professional duties and establish relationships in the work team, instability of behavior, that is, the inability of a person to pay professionally and insufficiently. Like all things, they evaluate their qualities negatively. Adaptation in society. The extent and persistence of the impact of these types of stereotypes leads to discriminatory attitudes towards disabled people in the labor market.

2. The choice of the direction or specialization of vocational education is often made by a person with a disability based on his physiological capabilities, degree of disability, educational conditions and access to it. The main idea of education is "Not where I can find a job in the future, but what I can do and want." Teaching young people with disabilities to analyze the real situation in the labor market from the perspective of personal capabilities is a field of work that needs to be implemented into the widespread practice of the employment service, which is part of the prevention of unemployment among employed persons.

3. Creation of jobs aimed primarily at providing employment to disabled people in enterprises and specialized organizations. The fact that the majority of unemployed citizens are graduates of secondary special and higher educational institutions is of particular concern. Among the disabled youth, programmers, economists and accountants, and lawyers are the most in-demand professions. An analysis of the most popular job vacancies for persons with disabilities showed that persons with disabilities are employed in low-skilled, monotonous, routine work and low wages (assemblers, security guards, tailors, quality control operators) demanding jobs are offered. This situation is related not only to the limitation of their individual physical or intellectual capabilities, but also to the underdevelopment of the labor market for persons with special needs. The employment system takes little account of the intellectual resources of the disabled. Many citizens with disabilities and mobility difficulties are capable of mental work: analyzing the situation, writing articles, works of art, creative work, research activities, etc. It will be possible to effectively solve the issues of providing employment to disabled people only when moving from traditional forms and methods of providing employment to citizens with disabilities to new, innovative methods based on the laws of the market economy. The following factors related to the behavior of the disabled in the labor market should be taken into account when choosing new forms and methods of employment support for citizens with disabilities of different groups of the population in the society. First of all, spatial and environmental problems. Even in cases where a person with a physical disability

has a means of transport (prosthesis, wheelchair, specially equipped car), the organization of life and social infrastructure do not meet the needs of life activities of disabled citizens. Getting a job without any complications is an insurmountable problem for many people with disabilities. Within this direction, the issue of obtaining reliable information about the situation on the labor market by a person with a disability is not resolved, which leads to inefficiency in solving professional problems. On the other hand, the society reacts badly to the problems faced by a person with a disability in searching for a job and working because he does not have complete information about this category of people. As a result, the potential professional potential of a disabled person is not fully utilized. The lack of information in the labor market also affects the situation in the field of education. Disabled people have limited access to vocational training. This is due to the inability of most educational institutions to educate people with disabilities and the slow development of the distance education system. The following issues affecting the employment of persons with disabilities include communication problems. Communication impairment is identified as one of the most important aspects of the employment and retention of a person with a disability in the workplace. It is related to a person's physical characteristics, his emotional state and the reaction of the work team. Emotional factors have a great influence on the effective behavior of a person in the labor market. This is, first of all, the ambiguous attitude of others towards a disabled person (embarrassment, ridicule, dissatisfaction, pity). People with disabilities themselves experience stress, fear, isolation and expectation of care during their careers. All this makes communication difficult and hinders the professional activity of a disabled person. The main issue in the labor market is the low cost of labor, which affects the economic situation of people with disabilities. The average salary for this category of citizens is much lower than for other categories of workers. It depends on the characteristics of professional activity (often unskilled, low-paid work). Despite the existence of certain privileges for the disabled, their level of financial support remains important. prevents. The labor market for people with disabilities can be differentiated based on the characteristics of the type of enterprise in which they work. Thus, the current situation in the labor market is very severe for disabled citizens, its main feature is the imbalance of supply and demand for labor force at the current stage, therefore, the presence of disability makes the process of providing employment to this category of unemployed very difficult. The position of disabled people in the labor market is determined by both subjective (low qualifications, inability to establish relationships in the work team, weak professional activity, etc.) and objective (low labor costs, poor infrastructure, poor information supply, etc.). Helping disabled people to work is a complex, multifaceted process of returning them to socially useful work or

engaging them in socially useful work, based on an individual approach to each client, according to their health, abilities and personal preferences.

References:

1. "On the rights of persons with disabilities" of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Adopted by the Legislature on July 22, 2020 approved by the Senate on September 11, 2020)
2. Teaching materials for the science of social adaptation
3. Internet information

